

NanoCommons Final Report - Contributions by UCD

Overview - University College Dublin (UCD) contributed to several Networking Activities (NA) such as Dissemination and Case study, with the lead role in two JRA3 (WP5 Analysis and modelling tools). UCD provided new multiscale modelling tools and data, and contributed to the development of integrated workflows and ontologies.

WP5 – Analysis & Modelling Tools: Purchase and installation of a computational server PowerEdge C4140 Server (DELL) system with 4 GPU (NVIDIA Tesla V100 SXM2 32GB GPU Accelerator for NVLink) and 2 CPU (Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 2.1GHz, 24C/48T, 10.4GT/s, 33M Cache, Turbo, HT-150W DDR4-2666) and 2 workstations with NVIDIA Quadro RTX 5000 at the Daedalus Data Centre of UCD for parallel computing, i.e., MPI and GPU for performing high-throughput calculations. A computational platform has been created for the developed tools and open source software (Deliverable 5.3). All software is efficiently implemented. Python scripts are used for the evaluation of computational data. Furthermore, we created MODA for each of the intrinsic and extrinsic descriptors following EMMC rules and application tools. Basic intrinsic descriptors as band gaps and extrinsic descriptors as immersion enthalpies in water and organic solvents (logP) were calculated for a variety of nanomaterials; related publication: [PCCP Hot paper 2021](#) on the intrinsic and extrinsic descriptors as well as bionano interface descriptors. Databases for many metals, metal oxides and carbon based materials of interest were created and data were listed in comparison to literature data if available. In the case of the immersion enthalpies we compared the data with calculated Hamaker constants (python tool based on atomistic force field parameters) and surface energies. MODAs for the following descriptors have been created: band gap, polarizability, ionization potential, electron affinity, Hamaker constant, immersion enthalpy, potential of mean force (PMF), adsorption energy of a protein on a nanoparticle.

- Corona tool provides through a multiscale model (UA) heat maps, i.e. minima of Boltzmann averaged orientations of pre-optimized protein structures on nanomaterials
- **Input:** PMFs, zeta potentials and Hamaker constants
- **Output:** Heat maps, i.e. adsorption energies of proteins on nanomaterials for a range of NM sizes and surface charges
- Implementation of corona tool in KB by BIOMAX (Deliverable 5.6)
- AOP service and publication:

Developed prediction tools for adverse outcome and toxicity pathways (AOP/TP) based on the likelihood of the molecular initiating events (MIE) and KeyEvents (KE). Catalogue evidence relating to relevant AOP/TP to allow identification of candidate MIE/KE events at bionano interface. Examples of such MIE/KE are: NM cell association and uptake, adsorption of NM at lipid membrane, binding a ligand in a given biological fluid, NM unfolding adsorbed proteins, production of reactive oxygen species, dissolution and ion release, etc.

First MIE prediction tool has been implemented and made available via web interface

Computational tool	Implementation	Methodology
MOPAC	GPU	HF (semi-empirical)
SIESTA	MPI	DFT
GROMACS	MPI, GPU	MD
GFN-xTB	MKL, OpenMP	TB-DFT and MD
LAMMPS	MPI	MD
CP2K	MPI	BOMD, DFT

Following TA has been completed in the first stage and a continuation is planned: Affinity ranking and abundance of specific proteins (selected model proteins inkl. allergens) in the nanoparticle biocorona was conducted using the United Atom tool in collaboration with PLUS. The work was achieved during a TA visit of Robert Mills-Goodlet from PLUS at UCD and calculations continued remotely from PLUS at the UCD workstations by an established remote access. *In vitro* experimental studies were conducted at PLUS and aligned with the *in silico* prediction tools emerging from the SmartNanoTox project coordinated by UCD. These assays included nanoparticle synthesis, surface coating, protein binding assays, physicochemical characterization, 3D folding assays, ELISA, and mediator release assays using patients' sera from allergic donors and rat basophil leukemia cell transfected with a human IgE receptor. At the GA 24 in Iceland (February 2020), it was decided to extend the ongoing TA with UCD into a case study, later termed Demonstration Case 2, and test different features integrated in the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase powered by Biomax and their functionality specifically in regard to aid data FAIRness. This work was, thus, carried on in WP9 and has meanwhile resulted in a scientific publication (see below).

TA & demo case on protein corona modelling & FAIR data

Computational prediction and experimental analysis of the nanoparticle-protein corona: showcasing an *in vitro-in silico* workflow providing FAIR data

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Other services which have been completed :

AOP service and publication:

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Two more are in progress:

Project reporting

UCD led deliverable reports D5.6, D5.7 and D15.1. Furthermore, UCD contributed to deliverable reports D4.3, D4.7, D5.3, D5.8 and D9.4 and reviewed D1.3, D3.3, D4.4, D4.5, D5.5 and D9.1. Additionally, UCD was responsible for one milestone.

Selection of scientific papers achieved by UCD acknowledging NanoCommons as funding source